

Morphodynamic processes and adaptive restoration of a vulnerable coastal segment in Georgia

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Abstract: The problem of protection and restoration of the coastal zone of the Black Sea of Georgia is very urgent at the modern stage. Widespread of erosion of seashores is usually caused by strong anthropogenic pressure on the natural system of the "river bed - seashore", which is related with the following factors:

1. Construction of hydropower plants, ports, water reservoirs;
2. Removal of material from riverbeds and beaches for construction purposes;
3. Construction of inexpedient coastal protection hydrotechnical structures and subsequent disturbance of coastal sediment balance within the coastal lithodynamic system ;
4. Ignoring the natural regularities, existing in the coastal zone, while still dominating of the rigid, technocratic approach in the field of coastal management. Taking into consideration the Gagra experiment (80s of the XX century), the volume of material, required for the artificial restoration of the beach on the Ochamchire coast is calculated by a special formula.

Keywords: Coastal zone, Anthropogenic pressure, Lithodynamic system, sea shores, sediment flow

Introduction

It is known that the intensive erosion processes developed along the sea shores in Georgia are first of all connected with the strong anthropogenic pressure on the entire system of the coast – "river bed-sea shore" (Alpenidze, 2015: 4(3-1), 58-66; Alpenidze, January 2018; Peshkov, 2005). Among them are: construction of HPPs, ports, water reservoirs, extraction of inert material from riverbeds and beaches for construction purposes, building of hydro technical constructions and in general the implementation of a rigid technocratic policy towards the shores of the sea. Today, there is almost no place on the Black Sea coast of Georgia (except for the new delta of the River Rioni) where the washing of the shore is not observed. A significant intensification of field-practical and scientific-research works is necessary for a complete analysis of the crisis processes developed against the background of the accelerated rise of the world ocean level (Monioudi, 2014; Peshkov 2005). Among them are: construction of HPPs, ports, water reservoirs, extraction of inert material from riverbeds and beaches for construction

purposes, building of hydro technical constructions and in general the implementation of a rigid technocratic policy towards the shores of the sea. Today, there is almost no place on the Black Sea coast of Georgia (except for the new delta of the River Rioni) where the washing of the shore is not observed. A significant intensification of field-practical and scientific-research works is necessary for a complete analysis of the crisis processes developed against the background of the accelerated rise of the world ocean level. Among them are: construction of HPPs, ports, water reservoirs, extraction of inert material from riverbeds and beaches for construction purposes, building of hydro technical constructions and in general the implementation of a rigid technocratic policy towards the shores of the sea (Peshkov, 2005). Today, there is almost no place on the Black Sea coast of Georgia (except for the new delta of the River Rioni) where the washing of the shore is not observed. A significant intensification of field-practical and scientific-research works is necessary for a complete analysis of the crisis processes developed against the background of the accelerated rise of the world ocean level (Monioudi, 2014).

Materials and methods

The research area is the coastal zone of the Black Sea of Georgia. During the research morphodynamic, lithodynamic, statistical, hydrometeorological, cartographic, aerospace, field, comparative geographical and general scientific methods were used.

Analysis and discussion

In the 30s of XX century (1934-1936), one of the first and most powerful anthropogenic interventions on the coast occurred near Ochamchire, when a sharp violation of the natural lithodynamic system of the coastal zone was noted (Alpenidze, 2015; Alpenidze, 2018).

Its reason became construction of the military harbor and the breakwater surrounding it near the mouth of the River Mokvi, on the extreme northern periphery of Ochamchire. Thanks to filling of the entrance angle on the windward side, 200 thousand m³ of beach material was accumulated. To the south of Port breakwater, within the limits of the city, the volume of washout should have been the same, although it made 10 times more volume, i.e. 2.0 million m³, which should be explained by the excess (95-97%) of the washed-out shore-building, easily breakable, fine-dispersed clays. It is also known that the clay fraction can no longer participate in the balance of the beach material after moving into deep water by storm waves.

On the perimeter of Ochamchire and 40 km south of it, the condition of the shore changed radically: the sediment flow moving from the north along the coast of Kodori turned out to be discrete (interrupted), it became unstable, the coastline began to recede intensively and made up 4-5 m per year near Ochamchire (Peshkov, 2005; Kiknadze, 1993, 201-213; Kiknadze, 1990, 33-44).

On the shore, A 10 m high active cliff was developed, within the city coast limits in the 60s of the 20th century the land of 3.0 ha area was completely destroyed in a 150 m wide strip, and the total retreat of the bank was 220 - 250 m. At the same time, a 4.5 km long wave-reflecting wall was built to protect the coast, and 57 groins were built for it from the sea. This event amounted to 8.7 million roubles (at the exchange rate of 1960-1980), which is equivalent to approximately 10 million US dollars.

An interesting experiment was carried out in Gagra. Here, the construction of the groins' series was followed by the so called bottom washout (Archil G.Kiknadze –1993, pp. 201-213.,) (Kiknadze, 1990: 33-44) occurred in the coastal area of Tkhem-Holodnaya Rechka (in the outskirts of Gagra). In order to protect railway communication, in 1970-1972, 22 groins and 3 underwater breakwaters were built, and their "pockets" were filled with gravel material. Soon (1982), the amount of accumulated sediment in the windward area of a groin (1-1.5 km) amounted to 30 thousand m³ (Peshkov, 2005, Kiknadze, 1993: 201-213). Together with this, feeding of the Gagra coastal beach was stopped and there was observed wash off on the 5 km long beach. 10,000 m³/year of beach material was deposited in areas between groins (pockets). However, washing off was detected in another nearby area, similar events took place in Gagra, in a district of the River Reprua mouth. In order to protect the shore, first concrete blocks were

placed, and later an underwater two-traverse breakwater was built. However, next to these constructions, in front of Gagra Park, the width of the beach has decreased to 3-5 m. In order to stabilize the emergency condition of the Gagra beach, 32 groins and a breakwater wall were built. Construction of each groin next to it produced a new accidental fragment of the bottom washout.

Reckless use of steel-concrete embankment constructions has damaged more than one coastal area. There are many examples of them both in Georgia (Fig. №1) and in other coastal areas of the world (Kiknadze, JCR, № 6, 33-44; Kos'yan, 1997).

Fig. 1

For example, on the coastal perimeter in Ochamchire. At present, about 60 groins and embankment walls in a 5-6 km perimeter, 60-65% are actually either damaged or destroyed, a similar situation is observed at the mouth of Khobi river, Gudauta, New Athos, and other sections. During the implementation of the well-known Gagra experiment (Zenkovich, Schwartz, 1988, 201-209.) – about 3,5 million m³ of gravel material was pulled, and despite its high rate of wear (30-45%), the width of the beach created here was 65-70 m, and it has been in a stable condition for 40 years. Gagra's successful experiment can be used in Ochamchire and other sections of the coast, where the following formula was used to restore the shore: $V_0 = 2L\Delta B h$ where V_0 is the volume of the beach; L – design length of the beach; ΔB – beach width; h – Coastal bulwark mark.

As mentioned, one of the main factors of their degradation on the accumulative banks is related to the sharp reduction of alluvium entering the seashore. In this regard, along with the dams built on the Chorokhi River, the dam built on the Enguri River played an important role (Gelovani, 2021: 317-325).

From the moment Enguri-Hesi power plant was put into operation (1978), the conditions of a sharp decrease in the flow of water from the arch dam of the structure to the confluence (62 km) and the interruption of natural cleaning contributed to the appearance of puddles and ponds in the river bed, which created centers of local natural pollution and unsanitary conditions. In addition, before the construction of the River Enguri Hydropower Plant (HPP), the average annual discharge of water was 192 m³/s, the flow of floating material was 1.05 million m³, creeping-rolling (bed load) sediments – 116.0 thousand m³, and that of the beach-forming sediment - 370.0 thousand m³. Since 1978, the values of the mentioned parameters

have undergone a sharp reduction. From this time the River Enguri water discharge has decreased by almost 4 times, the volume of floated sediment discharge has decreased by 14 times, the amount of creeping-rolling/traction load material has decreased by 7.7 times, and the runoff of beach-forming material has decreased by 12.8 times. It is clear that the colossal (241,0 thousand m³) deficit of annual beach material by the river in the coastal section of the estuary had a direct impact on the dynamic processes of the coastal zone, and the tendency of strong washing off of the beach became stronger.

At the same time, along with the morpho and litho dynamic factors of the banks, hydro meteorological factors are very important, although they are poorly studied by us, and we can only discuss them by interpolation. In this regard, the observational material of Poti Hydrometeorological station (HMS) is the most representative. It can be seen that the south-western (33 %) and western (25 %) direction waves have the predominant condition, spreading almost in parallel to the shore. Because of this, these waves can form a relatively weak alongshore sediment flow. Often they also cause opposing (bilateral) migrations. The maximum parameters of the waves (H 8.5 M; L 90 m; T 9.4 s) for Poti beach are mostly typical for the winter season.

Maximum values of wave elements according to seasons **Table N 1**

Wave elements	Seasons		Annual, max
	IV-VIII	IX-III	
Height (m)	2.5-4.0	5.0-8.5	8.5
Length (m)	54-75	70-90	90
Period (T s)	7.2-8.6	8.6-9.4	9.4

According to Poti hms data, the picture of wave repetitions in the Kolkheti perimeter sea water area is quite colorful according to the gradations of their directions. However, the most (almost 54%) are southwesterly and westerly rhumb waves. Indeed, their heights reach values of 5.0 m and more. The westerly rhumb waves have also the maximum value (9.0 m) (Table, N 2). The segment of incoming waves on the coastal perimeter of the Poti area and, in general, the entire Kolkheti sea shore perimeter, is quite wide (2250) and extends from the southeast almost to the northern rhumb.

Elements of waves (height and directions) according to Poti Hms **Table, N 2**

Heights, (m)	SE	SW	W	NW	E	NE	S	N	Total
0-0.25	1.86	3.38	3.69	1.83	18.96	2.4	0.81	0.46	33.39
0.25-0.75	0.79	18.56	15.0	5.78	5.24	0.093	0.46	0.19	45.513
0.7-1.25	0.064	8.04	3.8	1.6	0.37	-	0.099	-	13.967
1.25-2.0	-	2.2	2.0	0.81	0.031	0.032	0.12	-	5.194
2.1-3.4	-	0.5	0.41	0.4	-	-	-	-	1.31
3.5-4.0	-	0.093	0.064	0.064	-	-	-	-	0.221
4.1-4.9	-	-	0.032	-	-	-	-	-	0.032
5.0-6.0	-	0.093	0.12	0.064	-	-	-	-	0.279
6.1-7.0	-	0.032	0.032	-	-	-	-	-	0.064
7.1-8.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.1-9.0	-	-	0.032	-	-	-	-	-	0.032
Total	2.114	32.898	25.18	10.548	24.602	2.525	1.483	0.65	100.00

A complex morphodynamic situation can be observed in the northern part of the Kakhaberi Plain coastal zone. Despite the artificial deposition of material on the beach in recent years, the situation is more stable on the beach near the airport, where in comparison with 2004-2005, currently the sea coast line has moved towards the sea by an average of 60-80 meters. The established situation shows us that the prevailing south-westerly direction storms here will

move the coastal sediment from the side of the River Chorokhi mouth in general to the north in the direction of the Cape of Batumi. A sharp shortage of material has been formed in the distance of 1-1.5 km north of the mouth of the Chorokhi River and when the storms pass here, not only the beach is washed away, but also the concrete road and wall of the boulevard built here in the beginning 2000s are being systematically damaged.

Such a process is completely regular, because if we look at the Fig N 2 (Saf'yanov, 1996), we will see that a significant part of the boulevard is located in the zone of storm waves splash, and the width of the modern beach is not large here. Following the mentioned section, the coast line to the north is stable and apparent accumulation can be observed at a distance of 1.5-2,0 km. till Batumi Cape (Gelovani, 2021: 317-325).

Fig. N 3

It is natural that the created situation has its own reason. Yet at the end of the 19th century, a special hydro technical construction was built here, within the Batumi cape limits. which then first delayed and then completely stopped the movement of sediment along the shore. In the twentieth century, the extension of the construction towards the (lit) sea took place, which further strengthened the accumulation. As a result of the process, the material was accumulated not only on the land, but also on the underwater slope. As a result of the mentioned process, the

material accumulated on the slope was periodically moved underwater to the great depths of the underwater canyon (according to the stationary observation data available in the 80s of XX century). The most obvious case of material being dumped on the strongly inclined slopes of the underwater canyon was observed in February 1999, when the above-water and underwater parts of the beach near the Batumi cape were cut off as a result of a moderate earthquake in Turkey (on a 150 m length of the shore). Fortunately, due to the winter period and dawn, no human casualties were reported.

A comparison of space images of 2004 and 2018 shows us a very significant increase of the shore in the distal part of the Batumi cape. The situation at Batumi cape is well characterized by the underwater planning conducted by us in October 2021 (Fig. N 3).

In the analysis of the map of the underwater slope near the Batumi cape, the movement of the isobaths towards the sea is clearly visible, which also indicates the excessive accumulation of material on the underwater slope. It can be said with certainty that the accumulation in the section of Batumi cape has reached the limit values. Thus, at any moment, a high-sloping submarine slope is still expected (due to natural unloading or seismic thrust) to break away to great depths, which will probably also involve an above water part of the beach. It is worth noting.

Conclusion

Against the background of the rise of the world ocean, as a result of the strong anthropogenic pressure, the sediment balance on the Black Sea coast of Georgia is disturbed almost everywhere. Georgia has a very successful experience in restoring beaches. At present, the measures of artificial restoration of the seashore are of a truncated nature. During construction in the coastal zone, in most cases, natural regularities are not taken into account. In the current situation, it is necessary to carry out a full-fledged monitoring of the morpho- and lithodynamic direction of the coastal zone.

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